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X-Ray the City! Ernest Fooks, modern planner in the new world.

Introduction

Australian society underwent considerable change due to the immigration of Europeans fleeing the onset and aftermath of World War II. Concomitantly the discourse of urbanism in Australia was never more prominent than during World War II and the re-adjustment period thereafter: "Millions of words of discussion and proposal about city sprawling and satellite towns were written" (Boyd, 1947: 103). The émigrés had a substantial impact on the discourse of town-planning, however they have received little recognition. This paper will discuss the contribution made by Ernest Fooks, émigré architect and town planner, to town-planning in Australia, highlighting his influential projects, indicating where his work has contemporary relevance, and considering the conservation of his town-planning schemes. Fooks' European modernist training set him apart from the local town planners: his presence in Australia is both unusual and significant. Between 1939 and 1948 he was instrumental in the development of suburban housing estates in Melbourne such as "Newlands", Coburg, and Ashburton; he also produced town-planning and urban redevelopment schemes for country towns such as Swan Hill, Wangaratta, Horsham, Seymour and Ballarat; and a regional redevelopment scheme for the Latrobe Valley. While these country schemes were never built, the design for Swan Hill was highly feted and publicised, and would have been the first town of modern design in Australia if realised: and thus had significant impact on town-planning in Australia. The paper will also discuss Fooks' 1946

text *X-Ray the City! The Density Diagram: Basis for Urban Planning* in which he proposed a new and socio-political method of assessing urban population densities, which still has relevance today. In addition the paper will consider the conservation of the Newlands estate, Fooks' largest built design, and uncover deficiencies in the current conservation process.

Historiography

The history of émigré architects and town planners to Australia in the twentieth century remains largely unwritten. Similarly the émigrés received little recognition during their professional lifetimes. While architects Frederick Romberg and Harry Seidler have been widely accepted within Australian architectural discourse, other European émigré architects require more research. The only other émigré architects included in the historiography of modern Australian architecture are Ernest Milston, Karl Langer, Fritz Janeba and Ernest Fooks; and mention of them is less than cursory. Architects such as Hugh Buhrich, who perhaps has a greater claim than Seidler for designing the first truly modern buildings in Australia, are practically ignored. And there remain émigré architects, such as Pavils Dreijmanis, former Chief Architect of Riga, Latvia; who were absorbed by the Australian profession and never gained public mention. Émigré architects and town planners have been represented in both Australian and American architectural history as internationalists who designed in much the same manner irrespective of their location. However, it would appear that much of the émigrés work in Australia often describes key aspects of Australian culture, thought and landscape while retaining their European heritage. The work is one of cultural lamination and hybridization, rather than cultural importation. That the Australian experience seems so different to that of émigrés to America may, in part, be accounted for by their reception in Australia. Some architects were able to migrate to America as nonquota immigrants or as part of the celebrity rescue programme of the Emergency Rescue Committee (Barron, 1997: 18-19). Whereas in Australia no special consideration was given, the European architects had to follow the same immigration procedure as all the other quota immigrants. The lack of value attributed to émigré architects and planners continued throughout their careers, with lowly appointments, lack of publicity, patronage and promotion. This also meant that many spent the beginning, or entire, of their Australian careers working for an architectural firm or government agency rather than in private practice. Despite all of this, some architects and town planners, such as Ernest Fooks, managed to have con-

siderable influence on Australian architecture and town-planning.

Ernest Fooks

Ernst Fooks was born Ernst Fuchs on the 6 October 1906 in Bratislava, Czechoslovakia. Fuchs' distinguished tertiary education began in architecture at the Technical University of Vienna, and culminated, in a Doctor of Technical Sciences in town-planning at the University of Vienna in 1932. Fuchs' dissertation *Die Stadt in Streifen*, the linear city, was at the forefront of town-planning theory of the time. The same year that Fuchs submitted his thesis Nikolai Milyutin published his work on linear cities *The Problem of Building Socialist Cities* (Curtis, 1996: 253). Fuchs was clearly influenced by the Russian approach to linear cities; his ideal city was linear and divided into residential, leisure, city, business and industrial bands, with some functions being separated by isolation bands. The housing within his ideal city was influenced by Austrian and German practices of the time. He designed large, uniform courtyard blocks, 10 storeys high with U and T shaped plans. The courtyards contained kindergartens, schools and other communal functions. The low-rise apartment blocks he designed were in a Zeilenbau formation.

After completing his doctoral thesis Fuchs worked for Theiss and Jaksch on one of the earliest high rise housing blocks in central Vienna. In 1932 his partnership Atelier „Bau und Wohnung“ won a competition organized by the Central Organization of Austrian Architects for *Das wachsende Haus*. He continued to be interested in town-planning and won several town-planning competitions. Austria became increasingly difficult for Fuchs throughout the 1930s, as he was a socialist as well as a Jew; he migrated to Australia via Canada in 1938-9.

In 1939 Fuchs gained a position with the newly formed Housing Commission, Victoria, HCV. He worked for the HCV from 1939 until he set up private practice in 1948. In the 1940s Fuchs established himself as an active participant in the local town-planning and artistic communities. He became the first lecturer in Town and Regional Planning at the Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology in 1944, a position he held until 1954. He changed his name to Ernest Fooks in 1945 when he became an Australian citizen. He wrote numerous articles for Australian journals and in 1946 he published *X-Ray the City! The Density Diagram: Basis for Urban Planning*. In 1948 Fooks resigned from the HCV due to the lack of recognition he had received there and established his own practice. His architectural practice gained Australian and worldwide recognition in the 1950s and 1960s for residences such as

Lansell Road Toorak, Tyalla Crescent Toorak and Howitt Road Caulfield and the Jewish Community Centre, Canberra. He continued in practice until his death on 4 December 1985.

Fooks at the Housing Commission, Victoria

Fooks' town-planning work in Australia was undertaken for the Housing Commission of Victoria. The HCV was established in 1938 as a result of the Housing Investigation and Slum Abolition Board of Inquiry of 1936-7. It was initially created in an attempt to abolish slums; it was concerned with the improvement of existing housing conditions, the provision of houses for persons of limited means, and zoning within Victoria (Housing Commission of Victoria, 1938-1939: 3). The HCV was formed just as popular and professional interest in town-planning burgeoned. The unity of the discourse of so-called postwar reconstruction was its most striking characteristic. „All were concerned with the need for a planned economy and full [male] employment, city planning, population planning, decentralization, regional and participatory planning, and planning with special emphasis on the urgency of slum clearance“ (Sandercock, 1990:141). The profession of town-planning in the 1930s and 1940s was made up of individuals from backgrounds such as architecture, surveying, politicians and social reformers. There was no specific training in town-planning in Australia until 1944; though some planners such as Walter Bunning and Margaret Feilman trained overseas. It was not surprising that they trained in Britain, as the discourse of Australian planning in the 1930s and 1940s was almost entirely determined by British, and to a smaller extent American, influences.

The architectural work of the HCV was prepared by the Architects Panel, which consisted of four architects, all the principals of private practices, who were contracted to prepare all the HCV's architectural work. Frank Heath was the member of the HCV in charge of zoning and the layout of housing estates, and he employed Fooks. Heath had read widely in the area of town-planning (though his reading seems to have been limited to English and the occasional American source), nonetheless his planning education was limited, especially when compared with his chief assistant who had undertaken both masters and doctoral degrees in town-planning. Much of the work prepared for the HCV by Heath's office was actually authored by Fooks. That Fooks was the author of suburban housing estates in Melbourne including „Newlands“, Coburg and townplanning and urban redevelopment schemes such as Swan Hill is at first suggested by the increased sophistication of schemes prepared by Heath's office during Fooks' employment. Schemes

for Fishermen's Bend, 1938, before his employ, and Golden Beach, Queensland 1960 after his employ, are not as accomplished as the aforementioned schemes. Furthermore, Fooks signature and handwriting appeared on critical drawings, such as preliminary freehand drawings and sketch layout plans for the schemes (Frank Heath Picture Collection). Fooks also claimed responsibility for these schemes in his curriculum vitae. To recognize Fooks as being the primary intellectual contributor to these schemes is not to criticize Frank Heath for being recognized as the author. It was, and still is, the convention in architectural offices that all work is attributed to the principals. Rather attributing Fooks as author of these schemes goes a long way in explaining why they differed from other schemes, and why they were influential.

Swan Hill

One of the earliest and perhaps the most influential schemes Fooks prepared in Australia was an urban redevelopment scheme for the country town of Swan Hill in 1940. Swan Hill was to be the first town of modern design in Australia (Fuchs, 1942: 83 and *Journal Taralgon* 1943, May 6: 1).. Fooks' scheme was ambitious, it was to improve the present day conditions and anticipate the future needs of Swan Hill by more than doubling the size of the town, There were seemingly vast differences between the linear city with KarlMarx Hof and Zeilenbau formation housing of Fooks' doctoral thesis and the layout for Swan Hill. However, European influences could be seen in the scheme. One of the most noticeable attributes of the Swan Hill scheme was the division of the residential areas into neighbourhood units, rather than the linear city approach. At first this would seem to have been influenced by the contemporary British and American interest in the neighbourhood unit. However, Fooks attributed his initial interest in neighbourhood units as coming from the similar but earlier Russian system of rayons (Fuchs, 1942 and Fooks, 1946). This Russian system conceived of several units which form a town: starting from the „houseblock“; then the „group“ centred around a kindergarten; then a „block“ or neighbourhood unit centred around a primary school; and then a rayon which contains a larger number of community facilities and so on (Fuchs, 1942). These neighbourhood units are not the self-contained residential units proposed by the American author Clarence Perry in *Housing for the Machine Age*. Another notable part of the scheme is the considerable area given over to parks and recreational space. Not all of the influences for the Swan Hill plan were European, Fooks' highly regimented process in determining neighbourhood units

owed a lot to Lewis Mumford's notion of functional spotting. The street layout and use of culs-de-sac was clearly influenced by Garden City/Suburb notions that were the dominant practice in planning in Australia. Similarly influenced by Australian practice was the preference for the single-family house: though large residential apartment blocks in both Zeilenbau formation and courtyard arrangements were used sparingly throughout the scheme. The Swan Hill scheme represents a progression from Fooks' doctoral thesis. His use of British and American planning ideals that had currency in Australia together with his European influences produced a unique form of town-planning.¹

The plan for Swan Hill was greeted enthusiastically by architects and planners of the time, and garnered interest from the public as well. It was reviewed to acclaim in professional journals of the time and Robin Boyd used the plan, alongside another Fooks scheme for Seymour, in his seminal text *Victorian Modern*, 1947, to point the way for town-planning in Australia to proceed (Boyd, 1947: 66 and 69-70). The scheme was part of the Housing and Planning Exhibition of 1943 prepared by the HCV. While initially intended to be shown only in Melbourne it was finally exhibited in one suburban and eleven rural centres, due to popular demand. Despite the acclaim and influence that the plan for Swan Hill provoked, it was never realised. One of the primary reasons the plan was never realised was that the decentralization of industry in the post-war period did not occur to the extent that the post-war reconstructionists had envisaged. Swan Hill today is not much larger than at the time that Fooks prepared his plan. However, the plan is testimony to the visions and ideals of the post-war reconstruction planners of Australia, and is an exceptional example of the confluence of influences in Fooks' work.

Newlands

Fooks prepared plans for the Newlands estate in Coburg between 1940 and 1943. Construction of the estate began in 1943 (Housing Commission of Victoria, 1942-1943) and was largely complete by 1953. Newlands was the second large-scale estate to be built by the HCV, with over 770 dwellings (Broome, 1987: 304) it was considerably larger than the first estate the HCV built at Fisherman's Bend, and was far more influential on the development of later estates. The Newlands plan was further removed from the ideal city Fooks conceived of in his doctoral thesis than Swan Hill, it represents the continuing absorption of Australian influences into his work, and the further development of his approach to town-planning. Yet there were still European influ-

ences in the design. Most notable was the minimal use of culs-de-sac. There was a high level of street connectivity to the surrounding areas; the Newlands estate was not the isolated residential unit many Australian, British and American town planners were advocating. Similar to his process in the planning of Swan Hill Fooks used the concept of the rayon or neighbourhood unit. Early sketch designs show that Fooks went through a Lewis Mumford type process of functional spotting for the Newlands estate: this led to the provision of community facilities, excellent proximity to facilities outside the estate, and the zoning of land to the north of the estate as industrial. The most striking feature of the subdivision is the extent of parkland around and within it, with the Merri Creek being the western boundary of the site. Much of the estate housing has a close visual connection with the creek and adjoining parkland. The terrain of the subdivision has been carefully considered: Connolly and Outlook Streets follow the line of the Merri Creek, other streets follow the contours of the knoll the estate is built upon. The sophistication of this layout was far superior to local contemporary schemes by other planners, and represents the maturation of Fooks' system of town-planning as later-described in *X-Ray the City! The Density Diagram: Basis for Urban Planning*.

Fooks did not design the housing on the estate but a wide variety of housing types including three storey walk-up flats, duplexes and detached houses were built in accordance with his master plan. They were unified by a limited material palette that largely consisted of clinker brick, terracotta tiles, and corrugated asbestos cement sheeting. Fooks provided the Newlands estate with a community focus; it had a shopping centre that included medical and dental clinics, estate administrative offices and eight shops situated in parkland in the centre of the estate. Each shop had an attached residence and a garden area between the shops; it was the first of this innovative type to be built by the HCV. Newlands was positively reviewed in the professional journals *Architecture (Housing in Victoria)*, (1945) and the *Australian Housing Bulletin (Neighbourhood Shopping Centres)*, (1950); the provision of large amounts of parkland and community facilities was noted. Today Newlands is one of few HCV estates not to be considerably disfigured. This is testimony to the provision of community facilities and zoning, considerable parkland and harmonious siting of Fooks' accomplished design.

X-ray the City!

After his many town-planning experiences including the design of the Swan Hill plan (1940), and Newlands (1940-1943), Fooks crystallized his

thoughts on planning in his 1946 text *X-Ray the City! The Density Diagram: Basis for Urban Planning*. In a period of time characterised, in Australia, by glib statements on town-planning this text stood out as a sensible manual. Amongst a more general discussion of townplanning Fooks proposed a new and socio-political method of assessing urban population densities. The motivation to write *X-Ray the City!* was to construct a shared and meaningful language for planners to discuss population density. For as Fooks wrote, „Overall density figures neither express the existing relation between the population and the built-up area, nor do they represent a basis for comparing density figures of various cities (Fooks, 1946: 43). This is because urban boundaries are arbitrary in nature. Overall population density is obtained by dividing population by area: thus widely differing density figures arise from different definitions of what constitutes an urban area (Mees, 2000: 184-186). In *X-Ray the City!* Fooks proposed a series of different density measurements, from overall or gross density, which included all developed and undeveloped land in a municipality or statistical area, to the more useful area and lot density that covered only residential land (Fooks, 1946: 73-76). When first published *X-Ray the City!* received much positive attention. It was reviewed worldwide in professional journals to critical acclaim². Lewis Mumford wrote that Fooks had „made a real contribution to urban analysis, and therefore to planning itself. (Mumford, 1947 to Fooks 7 September). Fooks was the first to set out such a method, though the British Government later devised a similar system in *The Density of Residential Areas* in 1952. *X-Ray the City!* is of contemporary relevance as density statistics are still frequently used and cited by planners. Incredibly the majority of density statistics prepared today still use the inferior method of overall density. Thus it is still difficult to compare density figures in a meaningful way; the problem that propelled Fooks to write *X-Ray the City!* still exists making his work more relevant than ever. His work may undergo somewhat of a renaissance in the future as planners such as Paul Mees discover and promote his method of measuring population densities.

Conservation of Newlands

While much of Fooks' influence on town-planning in Australia comes from his writings and plans such as that of Swan Hill; it is only in his work such as Newlands that the issue of conservation arises. Within the Australian discourses of planning and urban history conservation is a theme that seldom arises. Furthermore, there is little discussion of post-war planning or urban history; and this limited discussion focuses on theory and a history of issues

and policy rather than built fabric. Thus these discourses have little impact on the conservation of urban areas; architectural historians write heritage reports, and the discourse of Australian architecture directs the conservation of the post-war built environment. The historiography of Australian architecture has "successfully engineered significance for orthodox Modernism in terms of heritage" (Goad, 2000). This vision of modernism "hailed various individual architects (rather than firms) as prophets of modernism, heroes whose work has been codified as a sanctioned modernist aesthetic (Willis, 1997). However, other architects and their work have been represented as "aberrant or even unworthy of inclusion as part of built history" (Goad, 2000). While a villa by Harry Seidler or Roy Grounds is widely considered to be worth conserving, this narrow vision does not encompass much metropolitan or commercial architecture, architecture of the everyday, or the work of large government agencies. Within this discourse the conservation of government-sponsored estates such as Newlands has not been considered of great importance. With the exception of the innovative shop/house type, the importance and significance of Newlands is in the principles that guided its plan, rather than the individual built objects. At Newlands these principles included those which directed the sophisticated street layout, the provision of parkland, the zoning, and provision of community facilities. This further complicates the conservation of Newlands within a discourse that privileges the listing of specific buildings that mark significant change in aesthetics and taste" (Goad, 2000).

Despite this prevailing vision of modernism, the Newlands estate has some heritage controls, it is protected by the Moreland City Council's Heritage Conservation scheme (Hubbard, 1990). After a brief discussion, this study states that the Newlands Estate is of significance as one of the first large estates developed by the HCV, as one of the most extensive estates based on the low to medium density housing promoted by the British and American Garden Suburb and New Town theorists, and due to its high degree of integrity. Yet the discussion so far has shown that the attributes for which Newlands is significant are more complex than this. Notwithstanding these heritage controls, it would seem there are deficiencies in the current conservation process of Newlands.

The discourse of sanctioned modernism within Australian architectural history leads to the marginalisation of estates such as Newlands by the authors of heritage studies. In the case of the Newlands study there is limited discussion of the history or description of the estate and elements of its

significance are overlooked. Thus when the estate is endangered by development, the planners and politicians who enforce the scheme do not have enough information to fully realise the significance of the scheme. This scenario has already occurred. In 1991 the shop/house shopping centre was demolished to make way for a new convenience store and the adjoining parkland was built over with housing. This obliterated the single most important part of the estate's built fabric, reduced parkland and number of community facilities on the estate; thereby diluting some of the guiding principles in the plan of the estate. If the heritage study had fully detailed the significance of the estate and its shopping centre, it may have been a more persuasive conservation tool. This case shows clearly the need for adequate documentation so that an appropriate conservation process will follow. It also points to the need for a wider, more rich and complex definition of modernism, or modernisms, beyond the sanctioned discussion of the heroes of modern architecture.

Conclusion

The development of Ernest Fooks' approach to town-planning can clearly be seen in the progression from his doctoral thesis to his 1940 plan for Swan Hill, his design for Newlands (1940-1943), culminating in his personal statement on town-planning, *X-Ray the City!* (1946). Initially his town-planning was based upon his European training, later he absorbed Australian influences, and developed an individual and hybridized approach to town-planning. His town-planning work such as Newlands sits outside the canon of sanctioned modernism of Australian architectural history, and thus its conservation is endangered by the limited approach to attributing significance within this discourse. Though the continuing exposure, recognition and analysis of the work and careers of planners and architects such as Fooks will add to the breadth and complexity of modernism in Australia. Until an understanding is reached between the disciplines of architectural history, and planning and urban history the work of someone such as Fooks' will not be fully appreciated. While the Australian discourses of planning and urban history include discussions of theory and a history of issues and policy they do not fully embrace the discussions of the built fabric of post-war urban areas or conservation. Perhaps if they did, the conservation of this part of Australia's heritage could be secured.

NOTES

¹Fooks' adaption to aspects of American and British town planning was later paralleled by Walter Gropius' town planning in America, for example in the New Kensington